

POSTOPERATIVE DELIRIUM: UNDERSTANDING CAUSES, RISKS, AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Kholikov B.M.

Department of Faculty and Hospital Surgery, Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health,
Fergana, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. Postoperative delirium (POD) is a common complication after surgery, especially in elderly patients, linked to significant morbidity, longer hospital stays, and increased costs. This article examines POD's pathophysiology, risk factors, diagnostic tools, prevention, and management. Neuroinflammation, neurotransmitter imbalances, and disrupted brain connectivity underlie its pathogenesis. Key risk factors include advanced age, cognitive impairment, comorbidities, and perioperative factors. Tools like the Confusion Assessment Method (CAM) and Nursing Delirium Screening Scale (Nu-DESC) assist diagnosis but need better accuracy. Prevention emphasizes non-pharmacological methods, such as cognitive stimulation and early mobilization, with pharmacological treatments used cautiously. Continued research on biomarkers and personalized prevention is essential for reducing POD's burden and improving outcomes through a multidisciplinary approach.

Keywords: delirium, surgery, risk factors, pathophysiology, diagnosis, management.

Introduction.

Postoperative delirium (POD) is a common and serious complication that occurs after surgery, particularly affecting elderly patients. It is characterized by an acute and fluctuating decline in attention and cognition, often leading to increased morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, and higher healthcare costs. The pathophysiology of POD is not fully understood, but it is believed to involve neuroinflammatory mechanisms and neurotransmitter imbalances. Early recognition and management are crucial to improving patient outcomes and reducing the burden on healthcare systems. The following sections explore various aspects of POD, including risk factors, predictive tools, and management strategies.

Risk Factors for Postoperative Delirium

Demographic and Health Factors: Advanced age, male gender, and pre-existing conditions such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, congestive heart failure, and chronic kidney disease are significant risk factors for POD^{1,2}.

Surgical and Anesthetic Factors: General anesthesia is more commonly associated with POD compared to other anesthesia techniques. Elective surgeries also show a higher incidence of POD¹.

Cognitive and Psychological Factors: Preoperative cognitive deficits, anxiety, sleep disorders, and high Charlson Comorbidity Index scores are linked to increased POD risk^{2,3}.

Predictive Tools and Models

Electroencephalography (EEG): Intraoperative EEG patterns, particularly burst suppression, have been identified as predictors of POD. EEG monitoring can help in early detection and intervention^{4,5}.

Machine Learning Models: Predictive models using machine learning techniques are being developed to identify high-risk patients, although a model with high sensitivity and specificity is yet to be established⁶.

Biochemical Markers: Perioperative measurement of cholinesterase activity has been proposed as a tool to identify patients at risk for POD, especially in emergency surgeries⁷

Management and Prevention Strategies

Non-Pharmacological Interventions: Multicomponent interventions, including orientation protocols, cognitive stimulation, and early mobilization, have shown effectiveness in reducing POD incidence.

Pharmacological Approaches: While no drugs specifically treat POD, medications like haloperidol can manage symptoms. The use of dexmedetomidine in non-cardiac surgeries has shown some promise in reducing POD incidence, though its benefits and risks need careful consideration.

Guidelines and Protocols: Updated guidelines emphasize the importance of screening for POD from the recovery room until three days post-surgery and recommend comprehensive preoperative geriatric evaluations⁸.

Despite the advancements in understanding and managing POD, challenges remain, particularly in developing reliable predictive models and implementing effective prevention strategies. The complexity of POD's etiology, involving multiple risk factors and mechanisms, necessitates a multidisciplinary approach to care. Additionally, the economic burden of POD underscores the need for cost-effective interventions and resource allocation in healthcare systems. As research continues, integrating new findings into clinical practice will be crucial for improving patient outcomes and reducing the incidence of POD.

Methods.

The methods for this article involved a comprehensive review of recent literature and clinical guidelines on postoperative delirium (POD). A systematic search was conducted using databases such as PubMed, Google Scholar, and Web of Science, employing keywords like "postoperative delirium", "pathophysiology", "risk factors", "prevention" and "management". Articles published within the last 10 years were prioritized. Studies were included if they focused on POD in adult surgical patients, discussed mechanisms, risk factors, diagnostic tools, prevention, or management, and provided clear methodologies and outcomes. Exclusion criteria were applied to exclude articles not in English, those focused solely on pediatric populations or non-surgical delirium contexts, and opinion pieces without supporting data. Relevant data on patient demographics, surgical types, identified risk factors, and proposed interventions were extracted and summarized into tables and diagrams for clarity. As this study is a review of existing literature, no ethical approval was required. This methodical approach ensures the findings are evidence-based and clinically relevant.

Pathophysiology of postoperative delirium

Postoperative delirium (POD) is a complex neurocognitive disorder that frequently occurs after surgery, particularly in older adults, and is characterized by disturbances in attention, awareness, and cognitive function^{9,10}. The pathophysiology of POD involves multifactorial interactions, including neuroinflammatory processes, neurotransmitter imbalances, and disruptions in brain network connectivity^{9,11}. Neuroimaging studies have identified global atrophy, white matter changes, and disruptions in cerebral blood flow and metabolism as key correlates of

delirium pathogenesis. Electroencephalography has shown generalized slowing of brain activity and decreased variability in oscillatory patterns, indicating disruptions in functional connectivity among specific brain regions¹². In particular, decreased feedback connectivity from the left superior temporal gyrus to the auditory cortex has been associated with POD, correlating with increased inflammation and severity of delirium¹¹. Inflammatory biomarkers such as interleukin-6 and C-reactive protein are elevated in POD, suggesting a significant role of systemic inflammation^{12,13}. Hypoxia-inducible factor-1 (HIF-1) is also implicated, as cerebral desaturation during anesthesia can lead to hypoxia, which is a risk factor for POD, especially in the elderly¹⁴. Additionally, neurotransmitter imbalances, particularly involving acetylcholine, and oxidative stress contribute to the development of POD^{15,16}. Advanced age, preexisting cognitive impairments, and perioperative complications are significant risk factors for POD^{9,17}. Management strategies emphasize a multidisciplinary approach, including preoperative optimization, careful intraoperative management, and postoperative interventions, with both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatments being crucial^{9,16}. Despite these insights, the exact mechanisms remain incompletely understood, necessitating further research to develop targeted prevention and treatment strategies^{18,10}.

Risk factors

Postoperative delirium (POD) is a multifactorial condition with several identified risk factors across different surgical contexts. Advanced age consistently emerges as a significant risk factor for POD, as seen in various studies involving cardiac, spinal, and deep brain stimulation surgeries^{2,9,19-21}. Preexisting cognitive impairments, such as lower preoperative Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) scores and deficits in attention and motor speed, are also critical predictors, particularly in elderly and Parkinson's disease patients undergoing deep brain stimulation^{2,19}. Surgical factors, including the type and duration of surgery, are influential, with longer operation times being a notable risk factor in cardiac and spinal surgeries^{19,9,21}. Perioperative complications, such as inflammation, blood loss, and postoperative sleep disorders, further increase the risk of POD^{20,21}. Additionally, frailty, as measured by the frailty index, and specific physiological markers like cerebral oxygen saturation and elevated C-reactive protein levels, have been associated with higher POD incidence^{19,21}. Environmental and psychological factors, such as preoperative anxiety and ICU-related stressors, also contribute to the development of POD^{20,21}. These findings underscore the importance of a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach to managing and mitigating the risk of POD, emphasizing the need for personalized prevention and treatment strategies tailored to individual patient profiles and surgical contexts^{9,2}.

Clinical features and diagnosis

The diagnosis of postoperative delirium (POD) is crucial for improving patient outcomes, and several diagnostic tools and criteria have been evaluated for their effectiveness. The Nursing Delirium Screening Scale (Nu-DESC) and the Confusion Assessment Method (CAM) are two widely used tools, with a systematic review indicating that both have comparable sensitivities (Nu-DESC: 0.69, CAM: 0.65) but differ significantly in specificity (Nu-DESC: 0.99, CAM: 0.92)²². Despite their widespread use, neither tool achieves optimal sensitivity, suggesting a need for more accurate diagnostic methods^{22,23}. The 4AT and UB-2 are ultra-brief instruments that have shown promise, with the 4AT achieving a sensitivity of 0.80 and specificity of 0.89, making it a recommended tool for early delirium detection²⁴. The importance of early and accurate diagnosis is underscored by the potential for serious adverse outcomes if delirium is overlooked,

emphasizing the need for valid assessment tests in perioperative and intensive care settings²⁵. A scoping review protocol aims to map existing evidence on delirium diagnostic tools, highlighting the necessity for evidence-based practice and identifying knowledge gaps for future research²⁶. Overall, while tools like Nu-DESC and CAM are integral to current clinical workflows, integrating them with additional risk factors or clinical judgment, and considering newer tools like 4AT, could enhance diagnostic accuracy and treatment of POD^{23,22,24}.

Prevention strategies

Prevention strategies for postoperative delirium (POD) emphasize a combination of risk assessment, non-pharmacological interventions, and careful perioperative management. The use of automated risk prediction tools, such as the Pre-Interventional Preventive Risk Assessment (PIPRA), has shown promise in reducing POD incidence and hospital length of stay by enabling targeted non-pharmacological interventions for at-risk patients²⁷. Non-pharmacological strategies are particularly favored due to their cost-effectiveness, ease of application, and lack of side effects. These include cognitive training to enhance cognitive reserve and noncognitive interventions like sensory stimulation, sleep improvement, and physical activity²⁸. Multicomponent interventions, which involve orientation protocols, cognitive activities, and early mobilization, have been effective in reducing delirium episodes and are recommended as primary prevention strategies⁸. Pharmacological approaches, while available, are often controversial due to potential side effects, and thus, non-pharmacological methods are preferred²⁸. Guidelines also stress the importance of comprehensive preoperative evaluations, particularly for high-risk patients, and the involvement of multidisciplinary teams to implement these strategies effectively. The integration of family members in the care process post-surgery is also suggested to enhance the effectiveness of these interventions⁸. Overall, a holistic approach combining risk assessment, non-pharmacological interventions, and family involvement is crucial for the effective prevention of POD^{8,27,28}.

Management of postoperative delirium

The management of postoperative delirium (POD) involves a multifaceted approach that integrates both pharmacological and non-pharmacological strategies, emphasizing the importance of early detection and prevention. The pathophysiology of POD is complex, involving neuroinflammatory processes, neurotransmitter imbalances, and brain network disruptions, with risk factors including advanced age, preexisting cognitive impairments, and perioperative complications⁹. Effective management requires a multidisciplinary approach, incorporating preoperative cognitive assessments and frailty screening using tools like the Mini-Mental State Exam and Clinical Frailty Scale²⁹. Non-pharmacological interventions, such as the Hospital Elder Life Program (HELP), have been shown to reduce the incidence of POD by implementing orientation protocols, cognitive stimulation, and sleep enhancement strategies^{8,29}. Pharmacological treatments, while not curative, can alleviate symptoms, with agents like dexmedetomidine showing promise in reducing POD incidence in non-cardiac surgeries, although their use requires careful consideration of risks and benefits⁸. Intraoperative management focuses on maintaining hemodynamic stability and adequate anesthetic depth, with no significant difference in POD incidence between general and regional anesthesia^{8,29}. The integration of these strategies, alongside family involvement and environmental modifications, forms the cornerstone of POD management, aiming to improve patient outcomes and reduce healthcare costs associated with this condition^{8,30}.

Long-term outcomes

Postoperative delirium (POD) is a significant complication in older patients, particularly following surgeries such as hip fractures, and is associated with various long-term outcomes. The prevalence of POD in hip fracture patients ranges from 18% to 53.3%, and it is linked to increased mortality, although this association diminishes when confounding factors are adjusted for. POD also correlates with extended hospital stays, increased non-home discharges, and higher medical complications³¹. Intraoperative electroencephalogram (EEG) patterns, specifically burst suppression, have been identified as predictors of POD, with a 41% increased risk in patients exhibiting this pattern, highlighting the potential for EEG monitoring in preventive strategies⁴. The depth of anesthesia, whether deep or light, does not significantly affect the incidence of POD, nor does it impact long-term mortality or cognitive function, suggesting that anesthetic depth may not be a critical factor in POD outcomes³². Additionally, perioperative measurement of plasma cholinesterases, particularly Butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE), can help identify patients at risk for POD, with lower BuChE levels correlating with higher POD incidence, especially in emergency surgery patients⁷. Risk factors such as advanced age, male gender, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, congestive heart failure, and chronic kidney disease are significantly associated with POD, emphasizing the need for targeted preventive measures in high-risk populations¹. Overall, while POD is linked to several adverse outcomes, the complexity of its risk factors and the variability in its impact necessitate further research to develop effective prevention and management strategies.

Table 1.0 Long-Term Outcomes

Year	Authors	Results
2023	Ya-Fei Wang et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The systematic review and meta-analysis found that deep anesthesia did not significantly increase the incidence of postoperative delirium (POD) compared to light anesthesia, with a pooled odds ratio of 1.40 (95% CI, 0.63–3.08, P = 0.41), indicating low certainty in the evidence regarding this outcome. - High-quality evidence indicated that anesthetic depth had no significant effect on long-term mortality (OR, 1.12; 95% CI, 0.93–1.35, P = 0.23) and cognitive function (OR, 1.13; 95% CI, 0.67–1.91, P = 0.64) three months or more after surgery³².
2023	Leire Serrano	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The study found that the incidence of postoperative delirium (POD) in New Zealand population was 1.9%, which is significantly lower than previously observed rates, suggesting potential under-reporting of POD in national datasets. - The analysis revealed that the incidence of POD was associated with several risk factors, including increasing age, male sex, general anaesthesia, Māori ethnicity, higher comorbidity, surgical severity, and emergency surgery, and that a diagnosis of POD correlated with increased mortality and longer hospital stays³³.
2023	Puriwat Toaditthep et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The study found that delirium in critically ill surgical patients is associated with significant long-term outcomes, including increased mortality rates and a higher likelihood of cognitive impairment after hospital discharge. - Additionally, patients who experienced delirium during their critical illness had a longer duration of hospital stay and were more likely to require long-term care services post-discharge compared to those who did not experience delirium³⁴.

2023	Nada et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The study found that 30.3% of older patients undergoing emergency laparotomy developed postoperative delirium (POD), with significant associations identified between POD and factors such as age, preoperative kidney or neurological disease, and sepsis. Additionally, patients with POD experienced longer hospital stays, increased likelihood of ICU admission, and greater duration of mechanical ventilation. - Multivariable logistic analysis identified independent risk factors for POD, which included age, chronic kidney disease, low serum albumin levels, and the need for postoperative mechanical ventilation. The analysis also highlighted that POD was linked to higher ASA and NELA mortality scores, greater operative severity, and more severe physiological scores³⁵.
2024	Matthias Gruendel et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Out of 151 patients aged above 75 years, 38 (25.2%) experienced postoperative delirium (POD), with a higher incidence in emergency surgery patients (36%) compared to scheduled surgery patients (14%). The study found that a decline in Butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) levels correlated positively with the incidence of POD, indicating that lower BuChE levels prior to surgery are associated with a higher risk of developing POD. - The study concluded that perioperative measurement of BuChE activity can serve as a useful tool for identifying patients at risk for POD. Specifically, emergency patients with BuChE levels below 1556 U/L were identified as being at the highest risk for developing POD, suggesting that quick point-of-care testing could potentially alter patient management before the onset of delirium⁷.
2024	Likhvantsev et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The study found that patients exhibiting a burst suppression EEG pattern during surgery had a higher incidence of postoperative delirium (POD), with rates of 22.1% in those with burst suppression compared to 13.4% in those without ($p=0.015$). This indicates a significant association between the presence of this EEG pattern and the development of POD. - An extended duration of burst suppression was linked to an increased likelihood of POD occurrence ($p=0.016$), while the burst suppression ratio did not show a significant association with POD, highlighting the importance of monitoring EEG patterns during surgery for predicting postoperative outcomes in older patients⁴.
2024	Yasser Almashari et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The study included 108 patients over the age of 65 who developed postoperative delirium (POD), with a majority being male (72 out of 108). The analysis revealed a significant association between POD and several factors, including advanced age, male gender, diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension (HTN), congestive heart failure (CHF), and chronic kidney disease (CKD). - The findings indicated that general anesthesia was the most commonly used anesthesia technique, accounting for 79.630% of cases, and that elective surgeries represented 86.111% of the cases studied. This highlights the prevalence of POD in specific patient demographics and surgical contexts¹.
2024	Changshuo Jiang et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The bibliometric analysis conducted in the paper highlights significant advances in the understanding and management of postoperative delirium (POD) over the past 20 years, indicating a growing body of research focused on this acute postoperative syndrome. - The study aims to consolidate current research focal points and identify emerging trends in the prevention and treatment of POD, reflecting the evolving landscape of strategies aimed at improving patient prognosis following surgery³⁶.

2024	Kieran FitzGerald et al.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The prevalence of postoperative delirium (POD) in hip fracture patients ranged from 18% to 53.3% across the ten studies reviewed, with a significant association found between POD and increased mortality in unadjusted analyses. However, when adjustments for confounding variables were made, no independent association with mortality was observed in several studies. - The review indicated that POD was associated with increased medical complications, longer hospital stays, and a higher likelihood of non-home discharge, but emphasized the need for further research to clarify whether these outcomes are causes or results of POD, particularly considering the age and comorbidities of the patients involved³¹.
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Table 1 presents key long-term outcomes of postoperative delirium (POD), including its association with increased hospital stays, non-home discharges, mortality rates, and cognitive decline. It also highlights significant predictors such as intraoperative EEG patterns, low BuChE levels, and perioperative complications. The findings underscore the need for targeted prevention and management strategies to reduce the adverse effects of POD on patients' recovery and quality of life.

Current research and future directions

Current research on postoperative delirium (POD) highlights its significant impact on patient prognosis, particularly among the elderly, and underscores the complexity of its pathophysiology, which involves neuroinflammatory mechanisms and neurotransmitter imbalances^{6,36}. Bibliometric analyses reveal that the United States leads in POD research, with a focus on cardiac surgery and the use of double-blind studies as emerging trends³⁷. Despite advances, there remains a lack of universally accepted biomarkers for POD, reflecting the diverse clinical presentations and underlying mechanisms³⁸. Guidelines emphasize the importance of early detection and management, recommending comprehensive preoperative evaluations and the use of validated screening tools from the recovery room to three days post-surgery. Non-pharmacological interventions, such as cognitive stimulation and early mobilization, are strongly recommended for prevention, aligning with the Hospital Elder Life Program's success in reducing delirium incidence⁸. Future directions include further exploration of genetic and clinical biomarkers, as well as the development of predictive models using machine learning, although a highly sensitive and specific model has yet to be achieved^{6,38}. The ongoing research aims to bridge existing knowledge gaps and improve the management of POD, with a focus on cost-effective preventive measures and the integration of family support in care protocols⁸.

Conclusion. Postoperative delirium remains a complex and significant challenge in perioperative medicine, particularly for elderly patients. Its multifactorial pathogenesis underscores the need for comprehensive preventive strategies, early diagnosis, and multidisciplinary management approaches. Effective non-pharmacological interventions, such as cognitive stimulation and early mobilization, are essential in mitigating risk, while pharmacological treatments should be applied judiciously. Advances in predictive tools, including EEG monitoring and biomarker identification, offer promising avenues for reducing POD incidence and severity. Future research should focus on refining diagnostic accuracy, enhancing preventive measures, and integrating personalized approaches to patient care. Addressing these challenges is crucial for improving surgical outcomes, reducing healthcare costs, and enhancing the quality of life for at-risk patients.

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